

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of
transformations research

Adapting to a changing reality. Policy recommendations from the GI-NI project

GI-NI Team

November 2024

POLICY BRIEF #7

This project has received funding
from the European Union's Horizon
2020 research and innovation
programme under grant
agreement number 101004494

GI-NI contributes to an inclusive Europe of shared prosperity by providing a better understanding of the changes and joint impact of three major transformations: technological progress, globalisation and migration; and offering policy and governance solutions to better equip citizens and companies for future challenges, securing more equal opportunities and outcomes. The project team uses a multidisciplinary research approach with international stakeholder engagement throughout the project.

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the GI-NI project Consortium and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

Summary

As the GI-NI project concludes, the European Union finds itself grappling with global challenges that demand policy recalibration. Set against the backdrop of the Green Deal and initiatives like the European Labour Authority, the project examined the EU's efforts to balance sustainability, labour mobility, and migration management. These efforts have been complicated by crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine, and growing isolationism in the United States. To prepare for the new European Commission that will start in 2025, the president of the Commission developed guidelines to address these shifts, focusing on globalisation, technology, and migration, but with notable imbalances. This **Policy Brief** discusses these guidelines from the perspective of the H2020 GI-NI project results. The GI-NI project underscores the interconnected impacts of globalisation, technology, and migration on inequality. Aligning the European Commission's 2025–2030 agenda with these findings is crucial to fostering a skilled, resilient workforce and equitable society.

Summary

Key messages

- Globalisation has been key to European prosperity, yet its benefits are increasingly scrutinised. While it has reduced inequalities between countries, it has deepened social divides within them. GI-NI's findings stress the need for open markets but warn of rising inequalities linked to global trade and technological shifts. A recalibrated EU policy must embrace multilateralism while addressing strategic challenges posed by China and Russia.
- Migration remains a crucial yet underdeveloped element of EU policy. The current focus on border security and returns overshadows the need for inclusion and integration. This defensive approach risks neglecting demographic challenges and labour shortages. Spain's proactive stance offers a potential model, emphasising the need for migration policies that integrate migrants into the workforce while fostering reciprocal development in their countries of origin.
- Technology, a driver of labour market transformation, remains under-addressed in EU policy. GI-NI findings show that technological advancements disproportionately benefit high-skilled workers, exacerbating inequalities and skill mismatches. While EU guidelines highlight technology as an investment priority, they fail to account for its broader social impacts. Principles from Industry 5.0—human-centric, sustainable, and resilient—could guide a more balanced approach.
- EU social policy remains fragmented, despite its potential to address inequalities. The European Pillar of Social Rights provides a framework but lacks ambition and coherence. Critical areas like housing, pensions, and intergenerational solidarity are underexplored. Stronger policies are needed to bridge gaps created by globalisation, migration, and technological change, with an emphasis on skills development, lifelong learning, and vocational training.

Recommendations

The GI-NI project calls for a recalibrated European agenda. Aligning policies with the realities of globalisation, migration, and technological transformation can address inequalities and build a resilient workforce. This shift requires moving beyond defensive measures to adopt inclusive strategies reflecting Europe's interconnected challenges.

Context

The H2020 GI-NI project was initiated within a policy context of the Green Deal, the establishment of the European Labour Authority, and the strengthening of the EU Border and Coast Guard Agency. The EU faced the challenge of balancing very conflicting ambitions: achieving a sustainable future, clarifying intra-EU labour mobility and managing the growing migrant crisis. The COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine and rising isolationist tendencies in the United States further reshaped the policy agenda. Consequently, the EU focused on advancing digital technology, promoting environmental sustainability, and strengthening social protections, such as introducing a minimum wage.

In December 2024, three striking examples illustrate how rapidly this reality has evolved:

- Northvolt, the Swedish battery manufacturer, once heralded as Europe's answer to Chinese battery dominance, is now teetering on the brink of bankruptcy. Despite €1 billion in EU-public funding, the company struggles with insufficient sales and delivery issues.
- Sweden has halted plans for several offshore wind farms, citing security concerns amid the ongoing war in Ukraine and the threat posed by Russia.
- Spain's government, led by Pedro Sánchez, has signalled an urgent need for increased migration to address labour market and demographic challenges—a stance notably divergent from the policies of most EU countries.

Today's shifting geopolitical and economic landscape calls for new priorities in European and national policies, with globalisation, technology, and migration taking centre stage. Ursula von der Leyen's Political Guidelines for the new European Commission¹ offer a strategic framework that reflects these changing realities. These guidelines, informed by the Draghi report², aim to address the evolving global balance of power and the rise of populism, which threatens to undermine European decision-making. Policies like the Green Deal represent significant achievements, but implementation remains fraught with challenges.

As the GI-NI-project concludes alongside the inauguration of the new Commission, this Policy Brief highlights how the project findings can refine and enhance these guidelines. It specifically identifies areas where current ambitions fall short or where policy measures lack the necessary emphasis. The GI-NI project underscores that technology, globalisation, and migration shape social conditions (in particular inequality, skills) in an interconnected manner. Policy responses must reflect this interplay. However, the current policy framework presents an imbalance, particularly in measures addressing technology and migration.

Navigating Globalisation's Shifting Landscape: Implications for Labour Market Inequality and European Policy

The European Union has long reaped the benefits of globalisation. However, since 2016, the merits of globalisation have come under increasing scrutiny. Today, the European Commission must address discussions of deglobalisation, especially in light of a potential tariff war under the new U.S. Trump administration (2025). To underscore the significance of globalisation, we conducted a scenario study exploring how technological change, globalisation, and migration collectively influence labour market inequalities. The findings indicate that labour market inequality between countries is minimised in a globalising economy (Los & Ye, 2023). Standards of living would also be higher if global trade and foreign direct investment would continue to intensify. Consequently, Europe must continue to advocate for open markets and find solutions for the growing inequality between countries. However, it is evident that the EU must shed any lingering arrogance and naivety in its approach to global economic relations.

The European Commission's new Guidelines reflect this shift, emphasising the pursuit of a level playing field under the framework of "A Global Europe: Leveraging Our Power and Partnerships." The Guidelines address unfair competition from China and its strategic partnership with Russia. The Commission acknowledges the changing global order: "Our rules-based international order is fraying, and our global institutions have become less effective," necessitating a stronger geopolitical stance and influence. Von der Leyen's strategy for globalisation emphasises four key components:

- **Guardrails:** The revision of the Public Procurement Directive focuses on protecting strategic products, fostering start-ups, and supporting innovators.
- **Quid Pro Quo:** Initiatives like the "Global Gateway," the "Strategic EU-India Agenda," and the "EU-African Union Summit" reflect a recalibrated approach to multilateralism and joint investments.
- **Strategic Investments:** The European Competitiveness Fund is set to bolster investment in critical technologies, reinforcing the EU's strategic autonomy.
- **Refocusing European Values:** Policies prioritise economic security and statecraft through initiatives such as "Clean Trade and Investment Partnerships" and the reform of the World Trade Organization.

While these measures signal reduced naivety, European arrogance may persist. Eurocentrism continues to dominate, with a disproportionate focus on developments in the "Old" EU. Moreover, the lack of alignment and diverse visions and interests among member states make it challenging to adapt to the changing global landscape. This needs to be clarified to understand the implications of globalisation for the New Member States (NMS).

The GI-NI project highlights that globalisation, while increasing value, also generates diverse social impacts, many of which still need to be better understood. These impacts should be integral to policy discussions on globalisation and technology:

- **Skill-Biased Technological Change:** Technological advancements tend to favour high-skilled workers over low-skilled workers across the EU, including in the Eastern EU (GI-NI: Reizer et al., 2024; Petó & Reizer, 2024).
- **Internal Labour Mobility:** The mobility of workers from Eastern EU to the West affects both receiving and sending countries. While wages rise in sending countries, the benefits are unevenly distributed across society (GI-NI: Lindner & Reizer, 2024). Gendered impacts are also evident, with Eastern EU women often faring better than men in terms of employment outcomes due to regional and functional specialisation.
- **Educational Mismatch:** Globalisation and technological change exacerbate educational mismatches. Many workers, in particular migrant women, are “overeducated” for their roles, leading to underutilisation of skills (GI-NI: Seghir & Smolka, 2024).
- **Labour Market Responses to Shocks:** The efficacy of labour market responses varies by country. For instance, workers in Germany benefit higher wages from seeking new opportunities when challenged by import competition, whereas similar strategies yield limited success in the Netherlands (GI-NI: Los, Konietzny, Peijen & Kraan, 2023).
- **Skill Mismatches and Inequality Rise in Most Scenarios:** Our scenario study revealed that the direction of (de)globalisation, combined with varying paces of technological progress, increases skill mismatches and inequality in most scenarios, even though the specific causes and new skill demands differ. Future developments in globalisation and technology are likely to further exacerbate social challenges (GI-NI: Matthijsen et al., 2024; Kampert et al., 2024).

The EU faces mounting internal discontent with globalisation. Future European policies must address these disparities and ensure that the benefits of globalisation are equitably distributed across regions and demographics. This requires a nuanced approach that accounts for regional specificities and integrates insights on labour mobility, educational mismatches, and gendered impacts.

Beyond Defensive Borders: Reframing European Migration Policy for Inclusivity and Sustainability

European migration policy is fraught with contradictions in its actions, values, and proposed solutions. While the EU has long recognised the centrality of migration to its demographic, economic, and social landscapes, its current policy frameworks reflect a predominantly defensive posture. The overarching theme of the European Commission's Guidelines is a defensive migration policy. Key directives emphasise border security and the return of irregular migrants. Phrases such as “Stronger Common Borders: integrated border management approach” and “EU Visa Policy Strategy to better secure borders and manage migration” highlight this approach. Similarly, initiatives such as the Pact on Migration and Asylum aim to ensure returns occur “in a dignified manner” and call for a “new Pact for the Mediterranean” to address regional migration flows. While these measures seek to manage migration more effectively, they risk prioritising control over inclusion, hindering integration of migrants in society and increasing inequality and polarisation. The policy overlooks the need for more sustainable and humane approaches by focusing disproportionately on return and border security.

A striking feature of the current EU migration policy is its opportunistic stance. The Guidelines suggest that migration should serve Europe's economic interests. They aim to “support Member States and companies with legal migration based on the skills needs of our economies and regions,” and “help match the skills of third-country nationals with labour market gaps in Europe.” Yet, there is a glaring absence of reciprocity: the Guidelines do not discuss how Europe can contribute to the development of migrants' countries of origin. This one-sided approach risks perpetuating inequalities between the EU and migrant-sending countries. It also ignores the long-term benefits of bilateral cooperation, such as the mutual recognition of qualifications and skills development.

Despite the rhetoric of dignity, Europe remains far from adopting a genuinely humane migration policy (Debono, 2019). Current thinking in European migration policy has stagnated. The GI-NI research project underscores the need for “tailor-made integration policies,” recognising that migrant inequality is not a monolithic issue but a heterogeneous one (GI-NI: Aldaz et al., 2024). These findings emphasise that migration is often driven by violence and insecurity rather than purely economic motives (Paul, 2020; GI-NI: Nikolova, 2023). Moreover, public attitudes toward migrants are partly shaped by the systemic poor treatment of these individuals³. Policies that fail to provide adequate opportunities for migrants to improve their conditions reinforce negative perceptions, further entrenching societal divides.

Migration is not new; it has been integral to Europe’s history for decades. Yet, the Guidelines largely ignore the integration challenges and discrimination faced by migrants already residing within Europe. Cultural differences are frequently exploited in the labour market, with female migrants disproportionately affected (GI-NI: Aldaz et al., 2024). Additionally, inadequate policies have exacerbated educational disparities between migrants and natives, significantly decreasing social cohesion and economic productivity (GI-NI: Seghir & Smolka, 2024).

In an era of rapid technological change, fostering educational opportunities for all, including migrants, is essential to ensure Europe’s adaptability. Failing to address these disparities undermines both the EU’s social and economic resilience. Migration policy sits at the nexus of globalisation, technological change, and inequality. Restrictive border policies may reduce migration flows in the short term, but they do little to address the root causes of societal tension: the persistent inequalities between natives and migrants within Europe. Without facilitating pathways for migrants to improve their social and economic positions, the attitudes of

³ There is a 60% rank-order correlation between poverty rate of migrants and host-country perception of the economic impact of migrants (the higher percentage of poverty of migrants, the less the host countries see migrants as having a positive economic impact). We used data from OECD/European Commission (2023), Figures 1.5 and 5.5. We excluded the Eastern-EU countries because of their low number of migrants.

native populations are unlikely to shift. A case in point is Spain's policy of framing migration as a solution to its demographic challenges, a strategy conspicuously absent from EU-wide discussions. With ageing populations and declining birth rates, many European countries share these demographic challenges. However, the current EU migration policy needs to adequately harness migration as a means to address labour market shortages or mitigate long-term inequality.

The EU must move beyond its defensive and opportunistic stance to embrace a more balanced and humane migration policy. Such a shift would entail:

- Developing integration strategies that empower migrants to contribute fully to European societies.
- Addressing inequalities in the labour market and education system to enhance social cohesion.
- Promoting bilateral and multilateral cooperation with migrant-sending countries to foster mutual development.

Only by adopting a more inclusive and forward-looking migration policy can Europe tackle its demographic challenges and labour market needs while upholding its human rights and equality commitment.

Bridging the Gaps: The Overlooked Role of Technology in Labour Market Inequalities and Policy Responses

The GI-NI project highlights the intertwined impact of globalisation and technology on skills and inequality. Technological change consistently exhibits a skill-biased nature across all examined EU labour markets. Arntz et al. (GI-NI: 2024) noted, “We find that frontier technology adopters significantly contribute to the economy-wide decline in routine and rise of non-routine cognitive jobs, primarily through firms with complementary workforce skills.”

Despite its significance, technology’s impact remains a blind spot in the European Commission’s guidelines. This is unsurprising, as technology and organisational policy often fall outside the traditional remit of government intervention. However, the need for greater investment in skill development persists. The guidelines primarily frame technology as an investment priority, with goals such as “boosting productivity with digital tech diffusion.” Initiatives like the European Data Union Strategy aim to pool technological competencies at the EU level, fostering joint technology development. However, achieving seamless collaboration remains a persistent challenge.

The guidelines notably need to include reference to the Industry 5.0 initiative (European Commission, 2021), which aligns closely with core European policy goals: human centricity, sustainability, and resilience. Industry 5.0 underscores the role of employees in technological development and implementation, advocating for their active involvement. As a driver of transformative change, technology reshapes globalisation's landscape. To address these shifts, organisations must adapt their policies to give workers greater control over technology.

Key Findings from the GI-NI project show the heterogeneity of impacts of technology on work:

- **Continued De-Routinisation:** Frontier technology adoption accelerates the decline of routine jobs.
- **Complementary Skills:** These are crucial for mitigating routine job losses and adapting to non-routine tasks.
- **Misleading Economy-Wide Conclusions:** Within-firm workforce adjustments do not necessarily reflect broader labour market trends.
- **Unequal Profit Sharing:** Additionally, companies that invest in advanced technologies enjoy higher mark-ups, translating into increased profits. However, this value is rarely shared equitably with employees.

Workers struggling to adapt to rapid technological change face significant risks in the labour market. As technology affects specific tasks across entire job categories, the solution to unemployment rarely lies in transitioning to adjacent roles. More comprehensive measures are necessary (GI-NI: Dabed et al., 2023).

The GI-NI research underscores the urgent need to address the growing inequalities and evolving skill demands across all educational groups driven by technological change. These technological shocks exacerbate inequality and continuously shift the skills required in the labour market. Solutions to improve labour market responsiveness to these shocks are complex and demand targeted research and intervention.

The Limits of Solidarity: Rethinking EU Social Policy in the Face of Global Transformations

The European Commission could, in principle, respond to the challenges outlined in the GI-NI project through targeted social policies, with the European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR) serving as a guiding framework. The twenty principles of the EPSR focus on three main dimensions of work: equal opportunities, fair working conditions, and social protection and inclusion. Ideally, the impacts of the three key transformations—technological change, globalisation, and migration—should be clear to policymakers. The Political Guidelines present a new action plan for implementing the EPSR. However, it is crucial to assess the scope and coherence of Europe's social policy.

Historically, European treaties did not place social policy at the core of EU governance (Hermans et al., 2023). It was only through ad hoc interventions that a European social policy began to take shape. Yet, this policy remains structurally flawed. Critics argue that the EPSR lacks clear political direction. Where political consideration exists, it is often described as “fundamentally neoliberal and market-oriented” (Ljungqvist & Sonesson, 2023). The reliance on the European Semester, driven by expert input, results in a largely technocratic approach (Elomäki & Gaweda, 2022). Moreover, the necessary trade-offs in social policy are deeply conflicting and cannot yield uniform solutions for all member states. While the EU has achieved historically high workforce participation and reduced poverty, wages have not kept pace with inflation (Gábos et al., 2024) and income inequalities remain to increase.

The selection of measures under the EPSR does not adequately address critical social issues. Some notable initiatives mentioned in the Political Guidelines include:

- **Social Fairness in the Modern Economy:** Action Plan for the EPSR, Quality Jobs Roadmap, and the EU's first Anti-Poverty Strategy. The Child Guarantee is also set to be strengthened.
- **A Union of Equality:** Investments in gender equality and LGBTIQ rights.

While these initiatives are commendable, they fall short of addressing the systemic challenges highlighted in the GI-NI project. The guidelines propose several measures under the theme of skills development:

- **Union of Skills:** Lifelong learning programs and the promotion of Science Technology Engineering Mathematic (STEM) education, with specific strategies to address teacher shortages and encourage more women in STEM fields.
- **Vocational Education and Training (VET):** A European Strategy to promote secondary VET qualifications.
- **Labour Market Adaptation:** Refocusing skills funding for twin transitions, developing a European Degree, and a Skills Portability Initiative, along with improving mutual recognition of diplomas across Europe.

These measures could help EU workers deal with the transformations. However, these measures largely sideline the role of migrants. In the best-case scenario, migrants are framed as a reserve labour force: “help match the skills of third-country nationals with labour market gaps in Europe and make it easier to attract the right talent through harmonised rules on qualification recognition.”

Key areas like intergenerational solidarity, pensions, and housing remain out of reach for coherent EU policy. These issues are deeply rooted in national contexts, with varied systems and frameworks across member states (Kucharska-Stasiak et al., 2022). Efforts to address pensions and housing inevitably confront structural differences in insurance and housing policies.

What needs to be more present is a unifying policy theory for the social domain. While the EPSR was designed in reaction to the austerity policies of the pre-2015 period, it lacks a forward-looking framework for cohesive social governance. In most member states, social policy reflects the political ideologies of governing parties, whether liberal, socialist, or conservative. Each perspective shapes policy choices based on finite resources and limited instruments. EU social policies similarly face constraints, particularly in the form of limited solidarity among EU citizens (Eick et al., 2024). Given these challenges, the EU is unlikely to achieve widespread success in the social domain, regardless of its policy direction (Natili et al., 2023).

Recommendations

The different GI-NI studies provide an extensive list of recommendations. We will not repeat them here. If the Policy Guidelines remain the main beacon for the new European Commission, then from the GI-NI perspective, the following changes should be integrated into the new policy.

- ***Recalibrating Policies on Technology and Migration***

The guidelines propose measures for advancing technology and fostering digital innovation, but these efforts must be better integrated with policies addressing labour market disruptions and skill mismatches. Migration policy remains underdeveloped. Spain's proactive stance highlights the critical role of migration in addressing demographic and labour shortages. Yet, across Europe, migrants are often seen as a stopgap solution rather than as integral to long-term workforce planning. Considering that national governments are in charge of the migration policymaking, it would be advisable to set some specific guidelines for all the member states to avoid policy discrepancies. By promoting European multilevel governance, European and national systems could be connected. Cooperation and coordination among local authorities and different government departments need to be implemented, along with the involvement of non-governmental partners in the policymaking process: migrant organisations, human rights organisations, NGOs, etc. In this way, policymakers can obtain different points of view from the diversity of stakeholders.

- ***Adapting the Social Agenda***

The interconnected impacts of these transformations demand a cohesive social agenda. Current policies must go beyond environmental and technological objectives to comprehensively address inequality and skills development.

A greater focus on upskilling and reskilling is essential, ensuring workers and firms are prepared for technological shifts and equipped to thrive in a globalised economy.

Conclusion

This Policy Brief recommends aligning the Political Guidelines of the new European Commission (2025-2030) more closely with GI-NI findings. Specifically, policies must address the compounded impacts of technology, globalisation, and migration to reduce inequalities and foster a resilient, skilled workforce. By doing so, the European Commission can ensure its policies are not only forward-looking but also grounded in the complex realities of today's world.

Further reading

Publications from the GI-NI project can be found on the website: gini-research.org.

Debono, D. (2019). Narrating the humanitarian border: Moral deliberations of territorial borderworkers at the EU's mediterranean border *Journal of Mediterranean Studies*, 28 (1), pp. 55 – 73

Eick, G.M., Im, Z.J., Leschke, J. (2024). Towards Social Europe? Obstacles and opportunities in the multi-level governance of welfare states *Social Policy and Administration*, 58 (4), pp. 545 – 553 DOI: 10.1111/spol.13046

Elomäki A., Gaweda B. (2022). Looking for the 'Social' in the European Semester: The Ambiguous 'Socialisation' of EU Economic Governance in the European Parliament *Journal of Contemporary European Research*, 18 (1), pp. 166 – 183

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Breque, M., De Nul, L. and Petridis, A. (2021). Industry 5.0 – Towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry, Publications Office of the European Union <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/308407>

Gábos, A., Binder, B., Branyiczki, R., Tóth, I.G. (2024). Unravelling the relationship between employment, social transfers and income poverty: Policy and measurement *Journal of European Social Policy*, 34 (3), pp. 289 - 308

Hermans, K., Greiss, J., Delanghe, H., Cantillon, B. (2023). Delivering on the European Pillar of Social Rights: Towards a needs-based distribution of the European social funds? *Social Policy and Administration*, 57 (4), pp. 464 – 480 DOI: 10.1111/spol.12879

Ljungqvist, M., Sonesson, A.(2023). All that glitters is not gold: The depoliticisation of social inequality in European education policy on 'microcredentials' *Journal for Critical Education Policy Studies*, 21 (3), pp. 153 – 188

OECD/European Commission (2023). Indicators of Immigrant Integration 2023: Settling In. Paris: OECD Publishing, <https://doi.org/10.1787/1d5020a6-en>

Natili, M., Ronchi, S., Visconti, F. (2023). Invisible social Europe? Linking citizens' awareness of European cohesion funds, individual power resources, and support for the EU *Journal of European Social Policy*, 33 (5), pp. 570 – 582 DOI: 10.1177/09589287231210727

Nato A. (2020). Downsizing the EU rule of law at the time of the European welfare system retrenchment *Diritto Pubblico Comparato ed Europeo*, 22 (4), pp. 1071 – 1094 DOI: 10.17394/99313

Paul, S. (2020). Characteristics of migrants coming to Europe: A survey among asylum seekers and refugees in Germany about their journey *Migration Letters*, 17 (6), pp. 825 – 835.

Project Identity

Project name

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of transformation research — GI-NI

Coordinator

Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast
Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO, Netherlands

Consortium

CNAM – CEET, Centre d'études de l'emploi et du travail (France)
University of Groningen (Netherlands)
Centre for European Policy Studies (Belgium)
University of Adger (Norway)
Centre for Economic and Regional Studies (Hungary)
Utrecht University (Netherlands)
Europa-Universität Flensburg (Germany)
University of the Basque Country (Spain)

Duration

2021 – 2025

Funding Scheme

Grant Agreement n° 101004494 — GI-NI — H2020-programme

Website

<https://www.gini-research.org>

For more information

steven.dhondt@tno.nl

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of
transformations research

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of
transformations research

www.gini-research.org